

A Review on Beamforming Approaches for Speech Enhancement

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Abstract

The main aim of this paper is to discuss speech enhancement techniques using delay & sum, complex Gaussian Mixture Model and Minimum variance distortion less response (MVDR) beam former. Using spatial filtering in microphone arrays results in increasing the required signal in the existence of environmental noise sources. These techniques i.e Delay and Sum Beam former(DSB), Minimum Variance Distortion less Response (MVDR) beam former and Complex Gaussian Mixture Model (CGMM) are implemented using multiple channel enhancement and the performance of these techniques were analyzed for different noises under various SNR levels. Improved speech qualities are optimized in time domain and frequency domain using beamformer approaches. The results shows that, rather than using delay and sum beam former technique the speech quality is improved with Minimum Variance Distortion less Response Beam former. The performance of different methods are analyzed using objective performance measures Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), Perceptual Evaluation of Speech Enhancement (PESQ).

Keywords: Delay and Sum Beam former (DSB), Minimum Variance Distortion less Response (MVDR) beam former and Complex Gaussian Mixture Model (CGMM), Perceptual Evaluation of Speech Quality (PESQ).

1. Introduction

In many applications of speech communications like speech coding, speech synthesis and

Figure 1: Basic Speech Enhancement Process

speech verification systems, the quality of speech and accessibility is decreased by environmental noise or random noise. From the last few decades, most of the researchers implemented various techniques

of speech enhancement to improve the quality of corrupted / noise signals. The techniques are broadly classified into single channel speech enhancement and multichannel speech enhancement techniques. In this paper, the multichannel speech enhancement techniques in which the corrupted signal is recorded using multiple microphones. On using array of microphones we can improve the speech enhancement.

Single channel speech enhancement is difficult task as only single speech is available. A technique to overcome this disadvantage is beamforming. In beam forming techniques, we include some spatial data in time i.e obtained by recording data at different locations.

2. Beamforming

Beam forming is the basic technique to improve the quality and intelligibility of corrupted speech signals. It utilizes the signals recorded with different microphones at different locations. Different beamforming techniques are classified as

- 2.1.Fixed Beamformer (Eg. Delay & Sum Beamformer)
- 2.2.Adaptive Beamformer (Eg. Minimum Variance Distortionless Response)
- 2.3.Complex Gaussian Mixture Model(CGMM)

2.1.Fixed Beamformer:

In the fixed beam former the parameters are fixed and does not depend on speech data. The coefficients or weights utilized for processing the noisy speech is fixed. Fixed beam former is also called as independent beam former. In this approach the weight of the coefficients don't rely upon receiver information. Delay sum beamforming is an example for fixed beam forming technique. The output for delay and Sum beamformer is mathematically represented as

$$\hat{s}(t) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M x_m(n - T_m) \quad \text{-----(1)}$$

Where, $\hat{S}(t)$ is the beam former output
 M is number of microphones
 $X_m(n)$ is signal received by the mth microphone.
 The delay sum beamformer operation is shown in Fig.2.

Figure 2: Delay Sum Beamformer

The position of main lobe's directivity pattern is modified by changing the phase weight, $\phi_m(f)$ which is specified by the following

$$\phi_m(f) = 2\pi\alpha(m-1)d \text{ ----- (2)}$$

i.e, $\alpha = \sin\theta / \lambda$

λ is to assess the wavelength and θ is the angle of incidence.

$$T_m = \frac{\phi_m(f)}{2\pi f} \text{ -----(3)}$$

$$T_m = 2\pi\alpha(m-1)d / 2\pi f \text{ -----(4)}$$

$$T_m = 2\pi(m-1)d \sin\theta / 2\pi f\lambda \text{ -----(5)}$$

$$C = f\lambda$$

$$T_m = (m-1) d\sin\theta / C \text{ -----(6)}$$

The Delay-and-Sum beam former (DS-BF) is one of the most straight forward approach and basis for various algorithms. As the name proposes, all microphone signals are time-moved and perform the addition operation over all signals. After the summation arrange all the samples and reconstruct the enhanced signal.

2.2.Adaptive Beamformer:

In adaptive beam formers, the weights are adaptively changed according to the speech data. These beamformers are very effective than to fixed beam formers like delay and sum beam former.

2.3.Complex Gaussian Mixture Model:

In CGMM method, the noisy speech signal is splitted into a sequence of blocks. After splitting the signal, we obtain the covariance matrix for each block and update the covariance in recursive manner. Initial covariance is obtained from aprori information.

3. Frequency domain processing for speech enhancement:

Figure 3: Flowchart for Time to Frequency conversion

The conversion of time domain to frequency domain is achieved by applying fourier transform on noisy speech. Later the beamforming is applied on the frequency domain signal. The processed or enhanced signal is reconstructed by applying Inverse Fourier Transform.

4. Signal to noise ratio:

Signal to noise ratio (SNR) is a calculation used in recognising speech which will analyse about the desired signals level with background noise. SNR is stated as the ratio of signal to noise power and it is conveyed in decibles. We can say that signal is higher than noise when the ratio is greater than 1:1. Most of the electrical signal is commonly used in signal to noise ratio whether it might be any signal SNR can be applied.

Signal to noise ratio is characterized as the proportion of the intensity of a signal (significant data) and the intensity of loud noise (undesirable sign).

PESQ lies between -0.5 and 4.5. If the distortion in enhanced speech is less than the PESQ value becomes high. PESQ is obtained by comparing the clean speech and enhanced speech signal by sampling rate of 8 or 16 KHz.

5. Minimum variance distortionless response:

This beam former works on the principle of minimizing the variance of noise components. This beamformer utilizes the time delays along with correlation between the different microphone signals.

Figure1. PESQ values for different types of beamforming techniques

Figure 2. SNR values for different types of beamforming

Here 3 types of beamforming techniques are considered, those are:

1. Delay and Sum
2. Complex Gaussian Mixture Model
3. Minimum Variance Distortionless Response

In figure 1 the graph is plotted between PESQ values and different Beamforming techniques. For Delay&Sum the value obtained is 1.14, for CGMM the value obtained is 1.16 and for MVDR the value obtained is 2.68. The main difference between three techniques varies with MVDR.

In figure 2 the graph is plotted between SNR values and different Beamforming techniques. For Delay&Sum the value obtained is 2.29, for CGMM the value obtained is 3.28 and for MVDR the value obtained is 6.15. The main difference between three techniques varies with MVDR.

6. Conclusion:

The beam forming technique can be applied for enhancing the corrupted speech. The working of Delay & Sum beam former and MVDR approaches has to be studied and the performance of various methods and analyzed using performance objective measures like SNR,PESQ.

From the results, it is observed that the MVDR beamformer provides better PESQ & SNR values when compared to other methods and hence it is concluded that MVDR provides superior performance.

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